

A STUDY ON VIEWS OF SMALL VENDORS REGARDING E-PAYMENT SYSTEMS IN HARYANA, INDIA

Dr. Pinki Rani

Assistant Professor of Commerce
Indira Gandhi University, Meerpur, Rewari, Haryana

Poonam

Research Scholar, Indira Gandhi University
Meerpur, Rewari, Haryana

ABSTRACT

Organised sector and unorganised (informal) sector both are the vital part of the Indian economy. Small vendors are the part of the informal (unorganised) sector of the economy. Small vendors are the persons who having low capital and with their efficiency and skill they run their business. In small vendors we consider street vendors, hawker, rehriwala etc. They are dependent on cash transactions. Due to demonetization, small vendors are mostly affected because there was cash shortage during the demonetization. So, during and after demonetization they have been transferred to cashless transactions modes over cash. In this study we will described the views of e-payment system among small vendors while using the cashless transaction modes. For the views of e-payment system accessibility, time, cost and security are considered in the study. The study has been based on primary and secondary data. The primary data has been collected with the help of well structured questionnaires. For the study we selected the small vendors from Rewari and Mohendergarh district of Haryana. Thus, the focus of the study is to know more about the concepts of e-payment system and its views of small vendors. Therefore, quantitative and qualitative data have been used. For analyzing the collected data we used frequency tables, percentages, t-test and ANOVA. The t-test and ANOVA are analyzing with the help of SPSS 20. The result of the study shows that there are no significant differences among small vendor's views regarding e-payment system.

Keywords: Demonetization, Small Vendors, E-Payment System

INTRODUCTION

Organised sector and unorganised (informal) sector both are the vital part of the Indian economy. Small vendors are the part of the informal (unorganised) sector of the economy. Small vendors are the persons who having low capital and with their efficiency and skill they run their business. They are dependent on cash transactions. Due to demonetization, small traders and vendors are mostly affected because there was cash shortage during the demonetization. Many of these small retailers are not equipped enough to make provisions of digital payments for their customers, and for this reason they are facing major hardships

(Kapoor & Khanna 2018). Despite this, there are many street vendors who are moving towards cashless payment by opting PayTM, Oxigen etc. The National Association of Street Vendors of India (NASVI) has also encourages and help the vendors to use e-wallets.

After demonetization, there was a change in the purchasing trends of goods and services. In market, vendors and shopkeeper are accepting payment through credit / debit card as well as through e-wallet. People were opted the cashless route of payment for goods and services. There are many offers and incentives offered by the e-wallet companies like pay through us and get “Some ” amount as cash back for making the transaction while some gave the discount offers (Kalyani, 2016).

Fig.1 Image showing Street Vendors start taking payments though E-wallet like PayTM.
Source: Kalyani, 2016

While making the purchase POS machine, is also used to make payment through credit / debit cards. After demonetization, it can be commonly seen at the petrol pump, vendors and/or in shopping malls. To make the digital cashless payment government has offered a discount on the POS machines so that the merchants or vendors can purchase them to get the payment from the customers.

Fig:2 Image showing announcing lowering down the price of POS machine
Source: Kalyani, 2016

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Yadav et al. (2016) studied the impact of organised retail on neighbourhood kirana stores: a case study of Malwa region in Madhya Pradesh. They studied the perception of small kirana shops in relation to the impact they can give and find also the effect on their employment. The study based on primary and secondary data having 70 respondents in Indore region through well structured questionnaires. The study result showed that kirana shops owner's profit is negatively affected; cost is increased to meet the higher service quality expectation of the customer in the competitive environment. There is positive impact on their employed due to growth of retail stores that was shocking point.

Kalyani, Pawan (2016) studied in paper the effects and shifting trends in marketing/purchasing to the alternative options available in the market and effects of demonetization in India. The data was collected by questionnaire. Result of the study show two aspects of demonetization, has both pros and cons. It is like refresh key in the Indian economy and flush all the dead deposited money into the economy, to the market through proper channels. It also help the economy sift from cash to cash less transactions with the help of many e-wallet companies like Paytm and other modes of e- payments like mobile banking , online shopping, e-wallets, online banking, credit cards, debit cards, UPI etc.

Arora and Arora (2017) measured the impact of demonetization. The aim of the study to find out that at what extent Indian people accepted demonetization as well as to know the perception of people towards black money and corruption. A well structured questionnaire was given to 400 people in Ahmadabad to obtain their responses. The hypotheses were framed on the basis of gender and measured the inconvenience and acceptance of demonetization among male and female. Independent t- test used to formulate the hypothesis. Both the Hypothesis accepted that was indicated that there is no significance difference

between inconvenience and average acceptance of demonetization among male and female. The study reveals that majority of the people believe that black money exist in country. Most of people believe that the government has been taken a massive action in form of demonetization.

Preethi, S. & Sangeetha , V.M. (2017) examined the impact of demonetization on various sectors of Indian economy. This study explored the reason of demonetization. These are make India corruption free, curb black money, control inflation, stop terror financing, more people pay income tax, Make a cashless society and create Digital India. The conclusion of the study told us demonetization policy is a step of financial reform in the country, but it is big decisions which have own its merits and demerits. These merits and demerits create big effect on country business and other economical activity.

Lata Sujatha T (2017) prepared a study in the titled “A Comparative Study on Pre and Post Demonetization on E-Banking Services” analysed how e-banking has evolved, were customers aware of these facilities prior to demonetization and how this act of Government affected public at large and pushed them towards using e-services. The study also concluded that in the period of pre-demonetization, banks were already taking efforts to make their customers aware of the new channels by conducting seminars etc. while in post demonetization, customers are more interested in privacy and security issues since usage of internet banking has become the medium.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To examine the views of small vendor’s regarding security, cost accessibility and time in e-payment system in Haryana on the basis of selected demographical variables.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

To achieve the above objective we formulate the following hypothesis-

Null Hypothesis –

H01- There is no significance difference between mean views of small vendors on the basis of gender regarding security, cost, accessibility and time in e-payment system in Haryana.

H02- There is no significance difference between mean views of small vendors on the basis of area regarding security, cost, accessibility and time in e-payment system in Haryana.

H03- There are no significance difference between mean views of small vendors on the basis of age regarding security, cost, accessibility and time in e-payment system in Haryana.

H04- There are no significance difference between mean views of small vendors on the basis of type of the business regarding security, cost, accessibility and time in e-payment system in Haryana.

H05- There are no significance difference between mean views of small vendors on the basis of monthly income regarding security, cost, accessibility and time in e-payment system in Haryana.

H06- There are no significance difference between mean views of small vendors on the basis of education level regarding security, cost and accessibility and time in e-payment system in Haryana.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research study is descriptive cum exploratory in nature. The study is based on both primary and secondary data. We study the effect of demonetization on small vendors of Rewari and Mohendergarh District (Haryana). Primary data are collected through questionnaires which are distributed at random to 100 small vendors. Out Of 100, 82 responses were eligible for analysis. Questionnaires have contains closed ended questions like, dichotomous questions, and Five Point Likert scale (Strongly agree to strongly disagree) questions. Personal survey method is used to collect data from the respondents. The question in the questionnaire is some questions are demographical informational and others are related with views of e-payments system like time, accessibility, cost and security.

For this purpose, various magazines, journals, research articles, newspapers and research reports have used for secondary data. Thus, the focus of the study is to know more about the concepts of e-payment system and its views among small vendors. Therefore, quantitative and qualitative data have been used.

Tool and techniques of data analysis

For analyzing the collected data we used frequency tables, percentages, t-test and ANOVA. The t-test and ANOVA are analyzing with the help of SPSS 20.

Limitation of the study

- The study only consider the small vendors of Rewari and Mahendergarh district as a sample it not considers other area like state and country vendors.
- Sometimes the respondents don't understand the importance of the study and therefore because of the fear of misuse of their information they don't reveal the true information or opinion.
- The present study only analyzing the data only some demographical variables. The future study may have including the others socio economic variable like marital status, family background etc.
- This study is considered only four factors of e-payment systems while further studies may be included some other factors of e-payment systems like trust, benefit etc.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1- Demographical Profile of Respondents

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Area	Rural	40	51.2
	Urban	42	48.8
	Total	82	100
Age	Less than 20	1	1.2
	21-30	28	34.1
	31-40	30	36.6
	41-50	22	26.8
	Above 50	1	1.2
	Total	82	100
Gender	Male	76	92.7
	Female	6	7.3
	Total	82	100
Types of Business	Vegetables Shops / Fruits Shops	3	3.7
	Stationery Shops/Medical Stores	9	11.0
	Kirana Stores/Milk and Dairy product shops	18	22.0
	Gift Shop /Boutiques / Ladies Shop	6	7.3
	Textiles / Baby shops	12	14.6
	Tea/Juice Stall/ Pan Bidi Shops	5	6.1
	Others	29	35.4
	Total	82	100
Education	Illiterate	4	4.9
	5 th	3	3.7
	10 th	7	8.5
	12 th	29	35.4
	Degree and Others	39	47.6
	Total	82	100
Monthly Income	Less than Rs.10000	20	24.4
	Rs.10001-Rs.20000	16	19.5
	Rs.20001-Rs.30000	15	18.3
	Rs.30001-Rs.40000	21	25.6
	Above Rs.40000	10	12.2
	Total	82	100

Sources: Compiled from Primary data

After collecting and compile the data we execute the above formulated hypothesis one by one.

H01- There is no significance difference between mean views of small vendors on the basis of gender regarding security, cost, accessibility and time in e-payment system in Haryana.

Table 2: Independent Sample Test

	t-test for Equality of Means						
	t	Df	Sig. (2 tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the difference	
						Lower	Upper
Accessibility	-.273	80	.785	-.06360	.23268	-.52664	.39944
Time	-.460	80	.647	-.15570	.33878	-.82990	.51850
Cost	-1.130	80	.262	-.40351	.35699	-1.11394	.30692
Security	.273	80	.785	.12427	.45481	-.78083	1.02937

Inferences: As we analysing the collected data we can found from the table that accessibility, time, cost and security p value is greater than 0.05 normally accepted significance level on the basis of gender. It means that men and women's opinion on views of e-payment systems is almost same on above factors.

H02- There is no significance difference between mean views of small vendors on the basis of area regarding security, cost, accessibility and time in e-payment system in Haryana.

Table 3: Independent Sample t- Test

	t-test for Equality of Means						
	t	Df	Sig. (2 tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the difference	
						Lower	Upper
Accessibility	-2.407	80	.018	-.28185	.11711	-.51491	-.04878
Time	-2.725	80	.008	-.46071	.16906	-.79716	-.12427
Cost	.971	80	.335	.18095	.18637	-.18994	.55184
Security	-2.533	80	.013	-.57778	.22809	-1.03169	-.12386

Inferences: as per collected data on the basis of area we can see that cost is having not significance because its p- value is (.335) is greater than normally accepted significance level, while remaining shows that there is a significance difference since the p-value is less than 0.05.

H03- There is no significance difference between mean views of small vendors on the basis of age regarding security, cost, accessibility and time in e-payment system in Haryana.

Table 4: ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Accessibility	Between Groups	4.380	4	1.095	4.274	.004
	Within Groups	19.727	77	.256		
	Total	24.107	81			
Time	Between Groups	.979	4	.245	.375	.826
	Within Groups	50.216	77	.652		
	Total	51.195	81			
Cost	Between Groups	3.128	4	.782	1.105	.360
	Within Groups	54.472	77	.707		
	Total	57.601	81			
Security	Between Groups	2.949	4	.737	.637	.638
	Within Groups	89.161	77	1.158		
	Total	92.110	81			

Inferences: As per table 4 accessibility's p-value is .004 which is less than .05, means age wise there is a significance differences in small vendors views. They don't think e-payment system is easy to use /easily accessible. While time, cost and security shows no significance differences in views.

H04- There are no significance difference between mean views of small vendors on the basis of types of the business regarding security, cost, accessibility and time in e-payment system in Haryana.

Table 5: ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Accessibility	Between Groups	1.909	6	.318	1.075	.385
	Within Groups	22.198	75	.296		
	Total	24.107	81			
Time	Between Groups	6.641	6	1.107	1.863	.098
	Within Groups	44.554	75	.594		
	Total	51.195	81			
Cost	Between Groups	5.397	6	.900	1.292	.271
	Within Groups	52.203	75	.696		
	Total	57.601	81			
Security	Between Groups	5.289	6	.881	.761	.602
	Within Groups	86.821	75	1.158		
	Total	92.110	81			

Inferences: Table 5 shows that accessibility, time, cost and security has no significance differences on various types of vendors that is different nature in business since all p-value is greater than normally accepted area (0.05). So we failed to reject the above null hypothesis (H04).

H05- There is no significance difference between mean views of small vendors on the basis of monthly income regarding security, cost, accessibility and time in e-payment system in Haryana.

Table 6: ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Accessibility	Between Groups	.384	4	.096	.312	.869
	Within Groups	23.724	77	.308		
	Total	24.107	81			
Time	Between Groups	4.145	4	1.036	1.696	.160
	Within Groups	47.050	77	.611		
	Total	51.195	81			
Cost	Between Groups	4.149	4	1.037	1.494	.212
	Within Groups	53.451	77	.694		
	Total	57.601	81			
Security	Between Groups	7.533	4	1.883	1.714	.155
	Within Groups	84.577	77	1.098		
	Total	92.110	81			

Inferences: The table 6 shows that there is no significant differences in views of small vendors regarding accessibility, time, cost and security on the basis of monthly income as p-value is greater than 0.05.

H06- There is no significance difference between mean views of small vendors on the basis of education level regarding security, cost and accessibility and time in e-payment system in Haryana.

Table 7: ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Accessibility	Between Groups	1.309	4	.327	1.106	.360
	Within Groups	22.798	77	.296		
	Total	24.107	81			
Time	Between Groups	13.030	4	3.257	6.572	.000
	Within Groups	38.165	77	.496		
	Total	51.195	81			
Cost	Between Groups	1.641	4	.410	.564	.689
	Within Groups	55.960	77	.727		
	Total	57.601	81			
Security	Between Groups	1.131	4	.283	.239	.915
	Within Groups	90.979	77	1.182		
	Total	92.110	81			

Inferences: The data analysis indicates that accessibility, cost and security have no significant difference as per education among small vendors, while time shows the significant difference.

FINDINGS

- From the study we can see that majority (92.7%) of male respondents in small vendors.
- Mostly (97.5%) small vendors are lies in 21-50 age groups.
- 47.6% respondent having higher education and other degree/diploma.
- On area and gender basis views having no significant differences, mean male and female small vendors as well as urban vendors and rural vendor's having same views on accessibility, time, cost and security of e-payments system.

CONCLUSION

As per the above analysis we can say that during and after demonetization small vendor's views on e-payment system having no significant differences on selected variables. Time is a factor where small vendors think that e-payment system is time consuming process. On the other hand, they don't think that e-payment system is secure. Fraud, hacking is the major issue that occurred in cashless transaction. Furthermore, the study reveals that e-payment system is accessible. Cash-back offers and discount offers make the digital transaction less costly. So, we can say that if e-payment system is became more secure and time saving small vendors would more and more encourage to use it.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Anjali Vig Kapoor and Prof. (Dr.) Parul Khanna (Dec, 2016), "Demonetization & Indian Retail: Pre-Empt the Future", International Journal in Management and Social Science (Impact Factor- 6.178), Vol. 04, Issue 12, ISSN: 2321-1784, Page No. 349-355.

Pawan Kalyani (Dec, 2016), "An Empirical Study of the Effect of Demonetization in India in the year 2016 and Analyzing Shifting Trends in Marketing/ Purchasing to the alternative Option", Journal of Management Engineering and Information Technology, Vol. 3, Issue- 6, ISSN:2394-8124.

Rajesh k. Yadav, Manoj Verma, Shriti Singh (2016), "Impact of Organised Retail on Neighbourhood Kirana Stores: A Case Study of Malwa Region in Madhya Pradesh", World Scientific News, e-ISSN 2392-2192.

Dr. Nidhi Arora, Poonam Arora (2017), "Measuring the Impact and Acceptance of Demonetization: A Data Extensive Analytical Study", Research Guru: Online Journal of Multidisciplinary Subjects (Peer reviewed). ISSN: 2349-266X, Vol. 11, Issue-2 (September 2017), Impact Factor- 3.021, PP 255-263.

Dr. T. Lata Sujatha (2017), "A Comparative Study on Pre and Post Demonetization on E-Banking Services", IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM), pp. 12-17, 2017. E-ISSN: 2278-487X

<https://www.dnaindia.com/india/report-vendors-get-street-smart-go-digital-2274852>